

1 **Pushing the limits of Geant4 precision and CPU efficiency for protontherapy treatments**
2 **with GAMOS**

3
4 **Abstract:**

5 **Background:** While modern commercial Treatment Planning Systems (TPS) have
6 incorporated simplified Monte Carlo methods to improve dose calculation accuracy, applications
7 based on general-purpose Monte Carlo are still widely recognised as the gold standard for
8 precision in radiotherapy. **Purpose:** To achieve better precision than the state-of-the-art
9 commercial TPS, we developed a detailed precise source model for the pencil beam scanning
10 proton therapy machine at Clínica Universidad de Navarra using GAMOS/Geant4. **Method:** Our
11 methodology includes a Courant-Snyder model using the Twiss Parameters to characterize the
12 beam envelope evolution, with three Gaussians for each coordinate, precise tuning of beam
13 energy accounting for propagation through the accelerator nozzle, and a comprehensive
14 analysis of all hadronic and electromagnetic models and parameters. We implemented an
15 automated fitting tool to match experimental data for each of the 98 accelerator energies.
16 **Results:** Using this approach, we achieved a beam description where 100% of points meet the
17 1%/1mm gamma criterion, and integrated depth dose (IDD) range precision within a few tens of
18 microns—exceeding the precision we could find in the literature. Our results challenge the
19 widespread use of the QGSP_BIC_HP Geant4 physics list, which is selected in virtually all
20 proton therapy machine Geant4 simulations since almost twenty years ago, demonstrating that
21 alternative Geant4 physics lists yield superior accuracy and reduced CPU time. **Conclusions:**
22 Through a systematic tuning of all Geant4 and GAMOS parameters, we achieved
23 unprecedented precision in simulating a proton therapy machine. Since GAMOS is an open-
24 source framework, this level of accuracy is now available for any current or future simulations
25 requiring high-fidelity proton therapy modeling.

26 **Keywords:** proton therapy, pencil beam scanning, Monte Carlo simulation, Geant4, GAMOS.

27 I. **INTRODUCTION**

28 The physical characteristics of proton therapy enable superior tumor control and sparing of
29 organs at risk. This also results in a lower frequency of late radiation-induced toxicities, making
30 it particularly beneficial for paediatric patients with a high probability of long-term survival¹. The
31 most advanced proton therapy technique is pencil beam scanning (PBS), where a thin beam is
32 scanned transversally using two scanning magnets, and multiple iso-energy layers are used to

33 cover the entire tumor volume. An advanced clinical application of PBS is intensity modulated
34 proton therapy (IMPT)²⁻⁴, which is increasingly available as more proton facilities adopt active
35 scanning technology. In IMPT, steep dose gradients can occur within the target, which makes it
36 highly sensitive to uncertainties in treatment planning.

37 To achieve the precision required for these conformal treatments, the proton dose
38 distribution within the patient must be predicted with the highest possible accuracy. Monte Carlo
39 simulation is widely recognised as the most precise tool for these calculations, as it models all
40 kinds of particle interactions on a particle-by-particle basis and accounts for tissue properties
41 using material properties. On the other side, routine clinical dose calculation is done with
42 commercial Treatment Planning Systems (TPS). While these tools, originally based on
43 analytical formulae, have recently introduced Monte Carlo simulations, such as AcurosPT in
44 Eclipse (Varian Medical Systems) and the MC algorithm in RayStation (RaySearch
45 Laboratories), they use a simplified version of Monte Carlo to speed up simulations, with
46 discretized energy loss and straggling tables and omission of the transport of gammas,
47 neutrons, and delta electrons.

48 In contrast, proton therapy simulations based on general purpose Monte Carlo codes, such
49 as Geant4⁵⁻⁷, FLUKA⁸, PHITS⁹ or MCNP¹⁰, provide a more detailed dose simulation. These
50 tools have proved their superiority not only with respect to traditional analytical TPS¹¹⁻¹⁵, but also
51 with respect to Monte Carlo-based TPS¹⁶⁻²⁰. Despite these codes are still not used to replace
52 TPS for clinical dose calculation, their high accuracy has made them invaluable as a research
53 tool to:

- 54 • Support decision-making at clinical facilities²¹⁻²⁵.
- 55 • Study the beam halo², which is crucial for small fields.
- 56 • Serve as an alternative to direct measurements for supporting the different stages of the
57 commissioning process of new proton facilities^{2,27-28}.
- 58 • Introduce radiobiological effects in dose calculations²⁹⁻³¹.
- 59 • Develop new technologies such as treatment range verification detectors³²⁻³⁵.
- 60 • Be used in verification methods for treatment situations involving large density and
61 tissue heterogeneities or metallic implants³⁶⁻³⁷.

62 Among publications using general-purpose Monte Carlo codes to simulate proton therapy
63 machines, there is significant variability in the chosen modelling approaches. The first variability
64 we can find is that some authors tune the beam parameters at a few discrete energies
65 (typically from 5 to 27) and interpolate for the remaining values, while others use all available
66 beam energies. For the energy distribution, most authors use a Gaussian shape, although other

67 distributions can also be found, like a third-order polynomial^{28,38}. There is also a wide variety of
68 options to simulate the beam position and direction distributions:

- 69 • A point source with angular divergence²².
- 70 • A 2D Gaussian distribution for the position with no angular spread, as it is considered
71 negligible³⁹⁻⁴¹.
- 72 • A 2D Gaussian distribution for the position plus a fixed angular spread^{38,42,43}.
- 73 • A 2D Gaussian distribution for the position and a 2D Gaussian distribution for angle
74 dispersion with a correlation between them given by on Courent-Snyder (Twiss) or the
75 Fermi-Eyges parameterisation^{20,44-46} or others^{14,48}.
- 76 • Regarding nozzle simulation, most authors model the beam at the nozzle exit, although
77 a few perform a detailed simulation of the nozzle geometry^{37,49-51}.

78 The precision reached in the fitting of experimental distributions is usually between 1 and a
79 few % or around one or a few 100 microns. Although this precision may suffice for many
80 protontherapy applications, there are some applications that require higher precision, such as
81 difficult treatments, very small fields, preclinical studies, or when other sources of imprecision
82 are reduced. In this paper we have aimed to reach a very precise matching to the experimental
83 data taken during the commissioning of the CUN Hitachi protontherapy machine, including the
84 testing or all the Geant4 physics options to improve the Geant4 precision while simultaneously
85 optimizing the CPU time.

86 II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

87
88 The proton therapy system installed at our hospital is the Hitachi ProBeat-CR (Hitachi, Ltd.,
89 Japan). This consists of a compact synchrotron that produces proton beams with 98 different
90 energy levels, between 70.2 and 228.7 MeV, corresponding to nominal R_{90} distal ranges of 3.9
91 and 32.4 cm in water, respectively. Here, the distal R_{90} is defined as the depth in water beyond
92 the Bragg peak at which the proton beam delivers 90% of its maximum dose. The current
93 configuration of the system includes a compact 360- degree gantry and a patient table with six-
94 degree freedom.

95 96 *2.1 Monte Carlo simulation tool*

97 During the last two decades, there has been an effort to develop toolkits based on general-
98 purpose MC tools which are more user-friendly for researchers and clinical staff working in
99 medical physics applications. Examples of such toolkits are PTSIM⁵²⁻⁵³, GATE⁵⁴ and TOPAS⁵⁵

100 for Geant4, Flair⁵⁶ for FLUKA⁵⁷ or PRIMO⁵⁸ for PENELOPE⁵⁹. One of these tools is the one
101 used in this work, GAMOS—Geant4-based Architecture for Medicine-Oriented Simulations—
102 version 7.0⁶⁰⁻⁶¹.

103 GAMOS was developed not only to be easy to use but also flexible, allowing users to utilize
104 any of the Geant4 features. This flexibility has also allowed us to make the studies explained in
105 this paper with simple script of a few tens of lines, which have needed only minor changes for
106 dedicated studies. The robustness of GAMOS is supported by its almost 20 years of history,
107 more than 4,000 registered users and over 100 scientific publications. In addition to the general-
108 purpose code, GAMOS has a set of utilities to make simulations in a given field, like PET,
109 SPECT or Compton Camera detectors, gamma spectrometry, gamma/electron radiotherapy and
110 also proton therapy, including radiobiological studies. Its flexibility has made it possible that a
111 sensible fraction of its user community works in other fields of physics rather than Medical
112 Physics, like High Energy Physics, Nuclear Physics, Space Physics, Radiation Protection, etc.

113 *2.2 Experimental measurements*

114 The experimental measurements used in this work are the same as those employed during the
115 commissioning of the Clínica Universidad de Navarra (CUN) commercial Treatment Planning
116 System⁶². For each of the 98 energies generated by the synchrotron, these measurements
117 include: 2D profiles in air at five depths in each of the two perpendicular directions, in-water
118 IDDs, and absolute doses following the TRS-398 protocol. Additionally, the dataset includes in-
119 water profiles for selected energies and a set of Spread-Out Bragg Peak (SOBP)
120 measurements, which include oblique fields and range filters.

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122 *2.3. Nozzle simulation*

123 The literature presents several approaches for simulating the nozzle of a proton therapy
124 machine:

- 125 • The entire nozzle is simulated in detail, and the patient dose calculation is performed in
126 the same job^{38,42-43,47,63}.
- 127 • The full nozzle is simulated in detail, and phase space files are accumulated after the
128 nozzle. These files are then used in a subsequent job to calculate the patient dose<sup>14,41,45-
129 46</sup>.
- 130 • The nozzle is not simulated directly; instead, beam parameters are fitted after the
131 nozzle^{20,22,64}.

132 We opted to fit the beam parameters after the nozzle, as this approach reduces CPU and
133 disk space requirements for simulating patient treatments. However, unlike previous studies that
134 rely on a simple Gaussian shape for the energy profile, we simulated the nozzle to obtain the
135 actual energy distribution after traversing the nozzle. Figure 1 compares the simulated energy
136 profile with a fitted Gaussian. The results reveal that the energy distribution deviates from a
137 Gaussian—even at low energies—and significantly diverges at higher energies.

138 Fig. 1. Simulated energy profiles after nozzle for several beam energies. Superimposed, in
139 dashed lines, are the Gaussian fitted distributions. Y axis has arbitrary units.

140 However, in addition to ensuring that the beam energy after traversing the nozzle is correct,
141 it is important to verify that using the same energy distribution for every beam position or
142 direction does not introduce any bias, as it is well known that particles at greater distances from
143 the beam center undergo more scattering, which can result in slightly lower energy and wider
144 energy dispersion compared to particles at the center.

145 Figure 2 shows for the energy distributions at each position bin: 1 minus the division of the
146 energy mean at that position and the energy mean at position 0, the same for the energy RMS,
147 and also the number of particles at each position. Similar plots were generated for energy
148 distributions at each direction bin. The results indicate that for the lowest energy (70.2 MeV), an
149 intermediate energy (150.2 MeV), and the highest energy (228.7 MeV), the change in mean
150 energy is negligible—always less than one per mille. The RMS shows larger differences at
151 extreme positions or angles, but the number of protons in these regions is two to three orders of
152 magnitude smaller, making the effect on the dose also negligible.

153 Fig. 2. Upper plots: \log_{10} of 1 minus the division of the energy mean at position 0 and the
 154 energy mean at a given position (top plot), \log_{10} of 1 minus the division of the energy RMS at
 155 position 0 and the energy RMS at a given position (middle plot) and \log_{10} of the number of
 156 events in each bin. Lower plots: same as a function of direction angle instead of position. The
 157 points after the vertical dotted bar represent the sum of bins higher than position 30 mm or
 158 higher than direction angle 1.5 degrees.

159 Since only protons will be simulated after the nozzle, it is also necessary to assess the
 160 contribution to patient dose from other particles generated within the nozzle. To do this, we
 161 simulated a beam of particles before the nozzle at the lowest, highest, and middle energies. We
 162 placed a water phantom starting 100 mm before the patient isocentre position (position -100),
 163 which we considered a good representation of the patient treatments. The upper plots in Figure
 164 3 show the integrated depth dose (IDD) and transverse dose profiles at the Bragg peak,
 165 separating the contributions from different particle types exiting the nozzle. These plots reveal
 166 that the contribution of particles other than protons is negligible—three to four orders of
 167 magnitude smaller than that of protons—except in regions beyond the Bragg peak at very high
 168 positions, where the total dose is negligible. The lower plots illustrate the contribution of

169 particles other than protons as a function of transverse position, and the conclusion is very
 170 similar.

171 Fig. 3. Contribution of the different types of particles to the IDD (upper plots) and transverse
 172 profiles at the Bragg peak (lower plots) for three different energies.

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174 **2.4. Beam shape**

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176 To determine the beam shape in position and divergence, we used 2D profiles measured in air
 177 at five planes: at the isocenter and at 100 and 200 mm at each side of the isocentre. The beam
 178 profile was simulated using three independent distributions with adjusted weights. For each
 179 distribution, we independently fitted the x and y coordinates using a beam characterization
 180 based on the Courant-Snyder particle transport theory: the sigma in beam size, the sigma in
 181 angular deviation, and the emittance.

182 By analyzing the 2D profiles, we observed that the ellipse defining the beam profile is
 183 rotated by a different angle for each beam energy. However, since the difference between the X
 184 and Y fits to a 1D Gaussian is in all except a few cases below 0.1 mm and always below 0.2
 185 mm, we did not account for this rotation. For each beam energy, we fitted the weighted sum of

186 three Gaussians, resulting in a total of 22 free parameters per energy. To reduce the CPU time
187 required to optimize all parameters, we developed an automatic procedure:

- 188 1. Independently for X and Y, and for each of the three Gaussians, the beam profile at the
189 nozzle exit was propagated to each of the five measurement planes using the Courant-
190 Snyder particle transport theory, while also accounting for scattering in air.
- 191 2. The three resulting profiles at each plane were then weighted relative to each other.
- 192 3. The final beam parameters were those that minimized the squared differences between
193 the simulated and experimental profiles at the five measurement planes.

194 Once the 22 parameters for a given energy were determined, a full simulation was run. The
195 results were compared to the 10 experimental profiles using a logarithmic plot. The criteria for
196 validating the simulation parameters were that, for doses greater than 0.1% of the maximum
197 dose, the ratio of the simulated dose to the experimental measurement was within a few percent
198 and never exceeded 20%. If these conditions were not met, the parameters were adjusted
199 manually. Given the large number of parameters used in the automatic fit and their high
200 correlation, it is common for the procedure to require several iterations.

201 The reason for using three Gaussians instead of two is that, although an absolute gamma
202 index⁶⁵ comparison (1%/1 mm) between experimental data and simulated profiles shows 100%
203 of gamma values below 0.6, a ratio of experimental to simulated values reveals significant
204 discrepancies at medium distances from the beam center (where the dose is approximately
205 10% of the maximum dose). Figure 4 illustrates these differences by showing the ratio of
206 experimental to simulated values for 2-sigma and 3-sigma Gaussian fits at three randomly
207 selected planes and energies.

208 Fig. 4. Ratio of experimental to simulated values (after normalization) for 2-Gaussian and 3-
 209 Gaussian optimal parameters at three randomly selected planes in the X or Y coordinates for
 210 different beam energies. Vertical lines indicate the positions corresponding to 1% of the
 211 maximum dose. Each subplot displays (top) the experimental values overlaid on the simulated
 212 values and (bottom) the ratio of experimental to simulated values. Y axis have arbitrary units.
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214 2.5. Beam energy

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 216 We simulated the beam energy distribution as a Gaussian, with the mean and sigma values
 217 fitted to the IDD measurements for each of the 98 energies. The variables studied include the
 218 distal range at 80% of the dose maximum, R_{80} , as well as the $R_{90} - R_{10}$ and the width at 80%,
 219 W_{80} , defined as the difference between R_{80} and the position of the 80% dose level before the
 220 peak. The mean excitation energy of water was set to 78 eV, as recommended in the Report 90
 221 of the International Commission on Radiation Units and Units⁶⁷.

222 2.6. Profiles in water

223
 224 Using the fitted beam profiles and energies described above, we simulated the profiles in water
 225 for three energies: 70.2, 142.5, and 228.7 MeV at three depths in the X direction and three in
 226 the Y direction.
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228 2.7. Monte Carlo absolute calibration

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 230 For the absolute calibration of the GAMOS simulations, i.e. the number of protons contained in
 231 a Monitor Unit, we followed the TRS 398 protocol as described in Azcona et al.⁶³. The
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233 difference between the number of protons per Monitor Unit used in the Treatment Planning
234 System and those obtained from the Monte Carlo simulations is within $\pm 1\%$ for all energies, as
235 shown in Figure 5.

236 Fig. 5. Difference between the number of protons per Monitor Unit used in the Treatment
237 Planning System and the ones obtained for the Monte Carlo simulations vs. the beam energy.

238
239 *2.8. SOBPs measurements*

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241 After fitting the beam parameters, we verified that the simulation reproduces the results for
242 several Spread-Out Bragg Peaks (SOBPs). One measurement point was taken for SOBPs fields
243 ranging from 2×2 cm² to 30×30 cm². Additionally, we included four off-axis fields, one oblique
244 field to assess beam rotation, and three fields with a range shifter.

245
246 *2.9. GEANT4 CPU and physics optimization*

247
248 Geant4 is designed as a toolbox: users must select among its various options those that best
249 match the requirements of their specific simulation setup. For proton therapy simulations, the
250 most critical Geant4 options include the hadronic interaction models and the models of
251 electromagnetic physics, including their optimization parameters, apart from the production
252 thresholds.

253 The hadronic models are organized in Geant4 through physics lists: users can select one of
254 the available physics lists which contains all the necessary models for all particles and all

255 energies. For proton therapy simulations using the Geant4 version we have used for this work,
256 11.01.patch03, there are four hadronic physics lists with different models to simulate proton
257 interactions at proton therapy energies: *QGSP_BIC_HP*, *QGSP_BIC_AllHP*, *QGSP_BERT_HP*
258 and *QGSP_INCLXX_HP*. As their names indicate they all contain the High Precision model for
259 neutron interactions, which uses the Evaluated Nuclear Data Files. In this version of Geant4 the
260 default database is *JEFF-3.3*, supplemented by *ENDF/BVIII-0* for materials not covered in
261 *JEFF-3.3*. Additionally, they all contain the Quark-Gluon String (QGSP) model, which is used to
262 simulate hadronic interactions at high energies (typically above 20 GeV), together with the
263 Precompound model, which is used for the de-excitation of excited nucleus resulting from the
264 hadronic interaction. For intermediate energies, down to a few hundred of MeV, the Fritiof (*FTF*)
265 model is used. The primary difference among the four hadronic physics lists is the model used
266 for the interactions of hadronic particles except neutrons at what is usually known in Geant4 as
267 middle and low energies, the energies used for proton therapy. *BIC* uses the Binary Cascade
268 model, *AllHP* uses the evaluated databases for protons, deuterons, tritons, helium-3 and alphas
269 for energies up to 200 MeV – and for higher energies it uses *BIC*, *BERT* used the BERTini
270 cascade model and *INCLXX* uses the Intra-Nuclear Cascade model. For further details on these
271 models, refer to the Geant4 Physics Reference Manual
272 (https://geant4.web.cern.ch/documentation/dev/prm_html/PhysicsReferenceManual/).

273 The four abovementioned physics lists also include different models and parameters for
274 electromagnetic physics. However, Geant4 also allows users to modify the electromagnetic
275 options by selecting different sets of physics constructors (in Geant4 terminology, a physics
276 constructor is a predefined set of physics processes, models and model parameters for each
277 particle). The physics constructors that offer better precision for medical physics simulations are
278 the so-called *option3* and *option4*. *option4* offers a better precision than *option3* at the cost of
279 increased CPU time. We did not limit ourselves to these predefined physics constructors.
280 Instead, we systematically studied how each of the Geant4 electromagnetic physics models and
281 their parameters influence both the physics results and the CPU time consumption.

282 Finally, we adjusted the production thresholds, which are designed to prevent the
283 generation of unnecessary low-energy secondary particles from ionization and bremsstrahlung
284 processes. These thresholds significantly impact CPU time: setting them too low results in the
285 creation of many low-energy particles that must be tracked, while setting them too high can
286 introduce bias into the physics results, as particles that would have reached a different patient
287 voxel are not created and their deposited energy is incorrectly summed in the voxel where the
288 last interaction took place.

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III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Beam shape

Using the 3-Gaussian parameterization, we compared the simulated profiles with the experimental ones at each of the five planes in air for every energy. To correct for any systematic offset of the experimental setup, we first shift the measured distribution so that the centroid mean of the fitted Gaussian is zero. We selected the sigma of a Gaussian fit as the figure of merit. Since the central part of the profiles fits well with a simple Gaussian, we preferred sigma over Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) because it is less subject to statistical fluctuations. Additionally, we included the Full Width at Tenth Maximum (FWTM) to assess the fit of the profile tails.

Figure 6 shows the differences in sigma and FWTM for all energies and depths. The difference in sigma is below 80 μm for all energies and depths, with most values below 40 μm . The difference in FWTM is below 200 μm , except for a few low-energy cases, and it is always below 400 μm . Part of this difference can be attributed to the precision of the experimental measurements. To estimate the contribution of this uncertainty, we constructed two new experimental profiles: one by mirroring the negative positions half and another by mirroring the positive positions half. The difference in sigma and FWTM between these two mirrored profiles provides an estimate of the experimental measurement's contribution to the discrepancy observed with the GAMOS simulations. We do not show the mirrored profiles for GAMOS as the deviations are quite smaller, thanks to the big statistics.

312 Fig. 6. a) Difference between the sigma of the profiles in air for GAMOS and experimental data.
 313 b) Difference between the positive and negative FWHM of the experimental data. c) Difference
 314 between the sigma of profiles in air for GAMOS and experimental data. d) Difference between
 315 the positive and negative FWTM of the experimental data. For clarity, the X axis represents
 316 energy+sign*(depth-250)/1000, where sign is +1 for X axis and -1 for Y axis.

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318 3.2. Beam energy

319 After fitting the experimental data to the GAMOS simulation data, we obtained energy values
 320 that differ slightly from the nominal ones, with deviations ranging from -0.8 MeV to +0.6 MeV.
 321 This is not surprising, as the beam energies provided by the vendor are nominal values.
 322 Similarly, the Treatment Planning System (TPS) also uses beam energies that differ by amounts
 323 comparable to those observed in the GAMOS simulations.

324 An absolute gamma index comparison 1%/1mm—where the percentage difference at each
 325 point is calculated as the ratio between the Monte Carlo (MC) and the maximum experimental
 326 value—yields gamma values never exceeding 0.15 for low energies and 0.5 for high energies.
 327 As shown in figure 7, for all energies, the R_{80} differences are below 50 μm , the R_{90} - R_{10}

328 differences are below 220 μm and the W_{80} differences are below 140 μm except for one energy,
 329 where it reaches 165 μm , slightly higher than for similar energies. Given the high statistical
 330 precision of our Monte Carlo simulations, we conclude that this deviation is likely due to
 331 uncertainties in the experimental measurements.

332 Fig. 7. Left plot: R_{80} of experimental data minus R_{80} or GAMOS simulation vs energy. Centre
 333 plot: same for R_{90} - R_{10} . Right plot: same for W_{80} .

334 3.3. Profiles in water

335 Figure 8 shows the difference in sigma and in FWTM between the GAMOS simulation data and
 336 the experimental data for the three energies and the six profiles per energy measured. The
 337 differences are bigger than the air profiles, but they are still quite low compared to other
 338 experimental results published. Similarly to the case of profiles in air, we also show the
 339 experimental distributions where the positions have been mirrored. While for sigma the
 340 differences in the experimental left half vs. the right half are quite smaller than the differences
 341 between experimental and GAMOS data, for FWTM—specially at low energies—they are
 342 similar. This indicates that a significant fraction of the difference between GAMOS and
 343 experimental data is due to the uncertainties in the experimental measurements.

344 Fig. 8. a) Difference between the sigma of the profiles in water for GAMOS and experimental
 345 data. b) Difference between the positive and negative FWHM of the experimental data. c)
 346 Difference between the sigma of profiles in water for GAMOS and experimental data. d)
 347 Difference between the positive and negative FWTM of the experimental data. For clarity, the X
 348 axis represents $\text{energy} + \text{sign} * (\text{depth} - 250) / 1000$, where sign is +1 for X axis and -1 for Y axis. For
 349 clarity, the X axis represents $\text{energy} + \text{sign} * \text{depth} / 10 / (\text{energy} / 70)^2$, where sign is +1 for X axis
 350 and -1 for Y axis.

351

352 3.3. SOBP measurements

353 Figure 9 compares the difference between GAMOS simulations and experimental data and the
 354 difference between the commercial TPS calculations and experimental data for the 47 SOBP
 355 fields. Considering that the experimental data point measurement uncertainty is 1-2% we can
 356 conclude that GAMOS simulation offers a good match to experimental data. On the other side
 357 TPS calculations show a higher discrepancy with the experimental data for small fields.

358 Fig. 9. Difference between GAMOS vs. data (black circles) and TPS vs. data (red triangles) for
 359 the different types of data. Error bars represent the statistical fluctuations of GAMOS simulation.
 360 No uncertainty has been considered for TPS nor for experimental data.

361 We also simulated the SOBP profiles using two Gaussians for each parameter and we
 362 found that for the small fields the discrepancy with experimental data was higher than 5%. This
 363 is another argument supporting the need to use three Gaussians to get precise dose
 364 distributions.

365 3.4. Geant4 physics options

366 The physics list used for almost all papers dealing with Geant4 for proton therapy is the so-
 367 called *QGSP_BIC_HP*, since Zacharatou *et al*⁶⁶ found in 2008 that the binary cascade model is
 368 the one that most closely reproduces experimental data. We compared with a precision much
 369 higher than the one used in Zacharatou *et al*. the four physics lists in Geant4.11.01.ref03 which
 370 offer significant differences among them for proton therapy: *QGSP_BIC_HP*, *QGSP_BIC_AllHP*,
 371 *QGSP_BERT_HP*, *QGSP_INCLXX_HP*. To compare the four physics lists we have used three
 372 sets of experimental data.

373 The first one is the profiles in water for the three measured energies. As Figure 10 shows,
 374 there is how no significant advantage for any of the four physics lists.

375 Fig. 10. Average gamma index 1%&1mm for the four physics list: *QGSP_BIC_HP*,
 376 *QGSP_BIC_AllHP*, *QGSP_BERT_HP*, *QGSP_INCLXX_HP*, plus for *QGSP_BIC_HP_EMY*. For
 377 clarity, the X axis represents $\text{energy} + \text{sign} * \text{depth} / 10 / (\text{energy} / 70)^2$.

378 The second set of data we used consists of the IDD profiles for a wide range of energies, from the
 379 minimum of 70.2 MeV to the maximum of 228.7 MeV, with steps approximately 10 MeV, i.e. 17
 380 energies in total. The first thing we realized is that different physics models give different proton
 381 ranges for the same beam energy. This means that we had to optimize the beam energy for
 382 each of the physics lists independently. Once this is done, we always found a very small
 383 difference in R_{80} , R_{9010} , W_{80} , indicating that these are not good figures of merit to differentiate
 384 the four physics lists. Instead, we checked which physics list better reproduces the full IDD
 385 profile. To do this, we compared the experimental and simulated IDDs using an absolute
 386 gamma index of 1%/1mm, and we calculated the average of the gamma values for all data
 387 points. Figure 11 shows this average for all the studied energies and the four physics lists. It can
 388 be clearly seen that *QGSP_BIC_HP* is not the best one, but *QGSP_INCLXX_HP* is.
 389 *QGSP_BIC_AllHP* yields similar values at low energies, but it is significantly slower.

390 Fig. 11. Average gamma index 1% / 1mm of the four physics lists as a function of the beam
 391 energy.

392 The third check we performed involved simulating real patient treatments to look for
 393 differences in the dose or Linear Energy Transfer (LET) distributions. We simulated three
 394 treatments: lung, breast, and craniospinal irradiation (CSI). A gamma index analysis showed
 395 that the differences between any pair of physics lists were not larger than the differences
 396 caused by statistical fluctuations (we used a sample size that resulted in a statistical uncertainty
 397 of approximately 0.5% in voxels receiving a dose greater than 20% of the maximum dose.) As
 398 expected, there is no significant difference among the different physics lists.

399 We have also observed other behaviours of the Geant4 physics lists that could be
 400 interesting for users. The first observation is that *QGSP_INCLXX_HP* and *QGSP_BERT_HP*
 401 are considerably faster than *QGSP_BIC_HP*: the CPU time is 40% slower for patient proton
 402 therapy simulations, using a production threshold of 0.1 mm. We found that the main reason for
 403 this is that lies in the electromagnetic models and parameters used: *QGSP_BIC_HP* and
 404 *QGSP_BIC_AllHP* use the so-called *G4EmStandardPhysics_option4*—with the only difference of
 405 including Auger electron cascade and atomic deexcitation, while *QGSP_BERT_HP* and
 406 *QGSP_INCLXX_HP* use *G4EmStandardPhysics*—with the only difference of including Auger
 407 electron cascade, fluorescence and Particle-Induced X-ray Emission (PIXE).
 408 *G4EmStandardPhysics_option4* is more precise than *G4EmStandardPhysics*, but at the cost of
 409 being slower. By changing each model and parameter, we discovered that the main CPU

410 difference is due to the use of the *Urban* multiple scattering model instead of the
 411 *GoudsmitSaunderson* model. In fact, *G4EmStandardPhysics* uses electromagnetic models and
 412 parameters already optimised for CPU time, so we decided not to change any option of
 413 electromagnetic physics to further optimize the CPU time of *QGSP_INCLXX_HP*.
 414 *QGSP_BIC_AIIHP* gives similar results than *QGSP_INCLXX_HP*, but it is around 40% slower,
 415 due mainly to the propagation of protons.

416 Some published papers use a version of *QGSP_BIC_HP* with optimised CPU time,
 417 *QGSP_BIC_HP_EMY*. This physics list uses *G4EmStandardPhysics_option3* and gives a CPU
 418 time reduced by 30% compared with *QGSP_BIC_HP* for the three patient treatments studied.
 419 However, by watching the water profiles in Figure 10, we observe that for high beam energies
 420 the difference with experimental data is bigger than for the other four physics list. For beam
 421 energy 228.7 MeV this model gives a mean difference of 0.28+-0.35 mm vs. 0.06+-0.07 for
 422 *QGSP_BIC_HP*, for 70.2 MeV and 142.5 MeV the differences are negligible. Therefore, we
 423 recommend using this physics list with caution. We traced back the difference to the use of the
 424 multiple scattering model *Urban* instead of the *GoudsmitSaunderson* model.

425 Last, we optimized the production thresholds in three real patient treatments used above.
 426 The results of CPU time w.r.t. to using a threshold of 0.05 mm are shown in table 1.

Production Threshold (mm)	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.5	1.0	5.0
CPU time	1	0.85	0.78	0.75	0.73	0.62

427 Table 1. CPU time using different production thresholds w.r.t. time for production threshold
 428 0.05 mm. Values represent the average across the three patients analyzed.

429 IV. CONCLUSIONS

430
 431 GAMOS/Geant4 has demonstrated high precision in modelling the beam of the CUN Hitachi
 432 proton therapy machine. Our study confirmed that simulating the nozzle using only the energy
 433 distribution of protons after traversing it and using the same distribution regardless of position or
 434 direction introduces no significant bias.

435 To fit the transversal profiles, we used parameters of the Courant-Snyder particle transport
 436 theory. Using three independent Gaussian distributions for each parameter achieved a precision
 437 of less than 1% in the sigma of the beam profiles in air. We also observed that using only two
 438 Gaussian distributions resulted in noticeable discrepancies with experimental data, particularly

439 in regions where the dose is approximately 10% of the maximum dose, plus a significant
440 reduction on the agreement of SOBP doses for low fields.

441 The precise fit of the IDD_s yielded a R_{80} precision better than 50 mm for each of the 98
442 energies, and a W_{80} precision better than 150 mm for all energies except one. Additionally, none
443 of the measured points exceeded a gamma index value of 0.5 (1%/1 mm criterion), with values
444 as low as 0.25 for low-energy beams.

445 We also evaluated with high precision each available hadronic and electromagnetic models
446 and parameters. Our findings revealed that *QGSP_BIC_HP*—the physics list used in almost all
447 previous proton therapy studies with Geant4—is not the most accurate or CPU-efficient option,
448 but rather *QGSP_INCLXX_HP*.

449 Using the final fitted model, we analyzed water profiles and found that the dose at all
450 measured points agreed with GAMOS simulations within 200 μm in sigma and 1.2 mm in spatial
451 agreement. Furthermore, all 47 SOBP measurements agreed within experimental uncertainties,
452 demonstrating superior agreement than the RayStation TPS currently used at CUN.

453 In summary, we achieved unprecedented precision in simulating a proton therapy machine.
454 GAMOS is a free framework which can be run in native Linux or Windows (with no virtual
455 machine), and we offer the models and the code used to achieve this precision for any current
456 of future simulations that may require it a precise proton therapy simulation.

457 In future work, we will use this framework to conduct a systematic study aimed at identifying
458 potential improvements in the patients' treatments planned with commercial TPS.

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